

A Study of Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. Students

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Abstract

The present study explores the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among B.Ed. students. Emotional intelligence plays an important role in controlling emotions, maintaining social relationships, and improving academic outcomes. A sample of B.Ed. students was selected using a random sampling method. Emotional intelligence was measured with the help of a standardized inventory, while academic performance was evaluated based on previous examination scores. The data were analysed using appropriate statistical techniques, including correlation analysis. The findings of the study indicate that there is a positive association between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. Students with higher emotional intelligence tend to perform better in their studies. The study emphasizes the significance of emotional intelligence in teacher education and suggests that it should be developed to enhance academic success.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Academic Achievement, B.Ed. Students.

Introduction

According to Peter Salovey and John D. Mayer (1990), emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, understand, manage, and regulate emotions in oneself as well as in others. It also involves the effective use of emotions to guide thinking and behaviour in different situations. In the field of education, emotional intelligence has gained increasing importance due to its strong association with students' learning behaviour, motivation, and interpersonal relationships. It significantly influences how students deal with academic stress, interact with others, and remain focused on their studies. Students with higher emotional intelligence are generally more capable of understanding their emotions, controlling their reactions, and adapting to academic challenges. These abilities help in improving concentration, confidence, and overall academic performance. In contrast, students with lower emotional intelligence may find it difficult to manage their emotions effectively, which can negatively affect their academic outcomes. Low emotional intelligence can result in problems such as anxiety, poor emotional control, and difficulty in managing academic stress, which may negatively influence students' academic performance. Academic achievement is widely considered an important indicator of students' learning and educational outcomes. For B.Ed. students, it holds special significance as they are future teachers who are expected to possess not only subject knowledge but also emotional maturity, empathy, and effective interpersonal skills. Hence, examining the association between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among B.Ed. students becomes essential for improving teacher education programmes and overall educational quality. Reviewing earlier studies is important for identifying research gaps, building a theoretical base, and refining the research methodology. It helps in understanding existing concepts, connecting previous findings, and comparing results across different studies.

Dutt Sharma (2021) conducted a study on emotional intelligence and emotional stability among adolescents and examined their relationship with academic achievement. The study was carried out on a sample of 300 adolescents using standardized tools. The findings showed that students with better emotional abilities and stability demonstrated improved concentration, confidence, and academic performance. Emotional intelligence was identified as a significant factor in maintaining emotional balance and enhancing learning outcomes.

Baduala T. (2022) investigated the impact of emotional intelligence on achievement motivation and academic performance among undergraduate students. The study included a sample of 250 students and used standardized measurement scales. The results indicated that emotional intelligence positively affects achievement motivation, which further contributes to better academic performance. Students with higher emotional intelligence were observed to be more motivated and academically successful.

Singhani Bhakti J. (2023) carried out a study to examine academic achievement in relation to mental health and emotional intelligence among secondary school students. The study involved 240 students and followed a correlational research design. The findings suggested that students with higher emotional intelligence showed better mental health and achieved higher academic scores, highlighting the importance of emotional balance in academic success.

Mishra N. (2024) carried out a comparative study to examine the impact of emotional intelligence, personality traits, and achievement motivation on the academic performance of day scholars and hostellers. The study was conducted on a sample of 300 undergraduate students using standardized tools for data collection. The results indicated that students with higher levels of emotional intelligence and positive personality characteristics achieved better academic results. Emotional intelligence was also identified as an important predictor of achievement motivation and overall academic success.

Hari P. (2024) investigated the role of critical thinking and emotional intelligence in influencing academic achievement in science among secondary school students. The study included a sample of 250 students. The findings suggested that both critical thinking ability and emotional intelligence have a significant impact on academic performance. Students with higher emotional intelligence showed improved analytical skills, creativity, and better learning outcomes.

Research Gap

A review of earlier studies shows that many researchers have explored emotional intelligence in relation to academic achievement among school and college students. Several studies have also examined its association with variables such as stress, motivation, personality, and mental health. However, limited research has been conducted specifically on B.Ed. students, who are future educators and have a significant responsibility in the teaching-learning process. Most previous studies have treated emotional intelligence as a general construct, while its specific relationship with academic achievement among B.Ed. students has not been adequately investigated. Additionally, there is a shortage of studies focusing on teacher trainees within the Indian context. Therefore, there exists a clear research gap in examining the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among B.Ed. students, which the present study seeks to address.

Statement of the Problem

A Study of relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of B.Ed. students.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of B.Ed. students.
2. To study the relationship between Intrapersonal Awareness and Academic Achievement Of B.Ed. students.
3. To study the relationship between Interpersonal Awareness and Academic Achievement Of B.Ed. students.
4. To study the relationship between Intrapersonal Management and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

5. To study the relationship between Interpersonal Management and Academic Achievement Of B.Ed. students.

Hypothesis of the study

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of B.Ed. students.
2. There is no significant relationship between Intrapersonal Awareness and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.
3. There is no significant relationship between Interpersonal Awareness and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.
4. There is no significant relationship between Intrapersonal Management and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.
5. There is no significant relationship between Interpersonal Management and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

Delimitations of the Study

- The scope of the study was confined to Saharanpur district only.
- The sample consisted of 100 B.Ed. students only.
- Emotional intelligence was measured using a single standardized tool.

Academic Achievement was delimited to the marks obtained by students in B. Ed First Year examination only.

Methodology of the study

Research Method

In this study, a descriptive survey approach was used. This approach helped in understanding how emotional intelligence and academic performance are connected among B.Ed students in real-life conditions.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study included 100 B.Ed. students from Saharanpur district. Students were selected using a random sampling method from two colleges. A total of 100 students were selected, with 50 students from each of two colleges.

- J.V Jain college, Saharanpur
- Gochar Mahavidyalaya Rampur Maniharan, Saharanpur

Variables

The study was based on two main variables:

Independent Variable: Emotional Intelligence

Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement

Tools Used in the Study

To collect the data, proper tools were used.

Emotional intelligence was measured with the help of Emotional Intelligence Inventory by **Dr. S.K.Mangal and Mrs. Shubhra Mangal (2019)**.

Academic performance was considered on the basis of marks obtained in the B.Ed. first year examination.

Statistical Technique Used in the Study

To understand the connection between the two variables, the Pearson correlation method (r) was used. This method shows how strongly and in what direction the two variables are related.

Findings and Interpretation

Objective -1: To study the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement Of B.Ed. students.

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed .students.

Table : 1

Variable	Number of students	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of freedom	Significant level
Emotional Intelligence Academic Achievement	100	0.58	98	Significant at 0.01 level

A Pearson's coefficient of correlation was computed between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement. The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.58 shows a positive and significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed students. Hence; the null hypothesis is rejected.

Objective -2 : To study the relationship between Intrapersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between Intrapersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed .students.

Table :2

Variable	Number of students	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of freedom	Significant level
Intrapersonal Awareness Academic Achievement	100	0.05	98	insignificant at both level

A Pearson's coefficient of correlation was computed between Intrapersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement. The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.05 shows a positive and insignificant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed students. Hence; the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective -3 : To study the relationship between Interpersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

H₀3: There is no significant relationship between Interpersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

Table : 3

Variable	Number of students	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of freedom	Significant level
Interpersonal Awareness Academic Achievement	100	0.047	98	insignificant at both level

A Pearson's coefficient of correlation was computed between Intrapersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement. The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.047 shows a positive and insignificant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed students. Hence; the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective -4 : To study the relationship between Intrapersonal Management (dimension of Emotional Intelligence)and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

H₀4: There is no significant relationship between Intrapersonal Management (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

Table : 4

Variable	Number of students	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of freedom	Significant level
Intrapersonal Management Academic Achievement	100	0.07	98	insignificant at both level

A Pearson's coefficient of correlation was computed between Interpersonal awareness (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement. The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.07 shows a positive and insignificant relationship between Intrapersonal Management dimension of

Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed students. Hence; the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective -5 : To study the relationship between Interpersonal Management (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students.

H₀5: There is no significant relationship between Interpersonal Management (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement of B.Ed students.

Table : 5

Variable	Number of students	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of freedom	Significant level
Interpersonal Management Academic Achievement	100	0.172	98	insignificant at both level

A Pearson's coefficient of correlation was computed between Interpersonal Management (dimension of Emotional Intelligence) and Academic Achievement. The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.07 shows a positive and insignificant relationship between Interpersonal Management dimension of Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of B.Ed. students. Hence; the null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to understand how emotional intelligence is related to the academic performance of B.Ed. students. Emotional intelligence was looked at both as a whole and through its four dimensions.

- I. Intrapersonal awareness
- II. Interpersonal awareness
- III. Intrapersonal management
- IV. Interpersonal management

The results showed that there is a clear connection between overall emotional intelligence and academic performance. Because of this, the idea that there is no relationship between the two was not supported. At the same time, when each part of emotional intelligence was studied separately, none of them showed a strong effect on academic performance on their own. This means that a single aspect of emotional intelligence is not enough to influence results. Overall, it can be said that emotional intelligence works better when all its aspects are taken together rather than individually. So, in teacher education programs, more attention should be given to developing emotional intelligence in a balanced and combined way to support students' learning and growth.

Suggestions for Further Study

1. Future studies may be conducted on a larger sample to get more reliable and generalizable results.
2. Similar studies can be carried out with students of other professional courses such as B.El.Ed, M.Ed, or B.A. B.Ed to compare the findings.
3. Researchers may study the relationship between emotional intelligence and other variables like motivation, self-esteem, teaching aptitude, or stress.
4. Longitudinal studies may be conducted to understand how emotional intelligence develops over time and affects academic achievement.
5. Comparative analysis can be carried out among male and female students and between urban and rural groups .
6. Experimental studies may be planned to see the effect of emotional intelligence training programmes on academic achievement.
7. Qualitative methods such as interviews or case studies can be used to gain deeper understanding of students' emotional experiences.

References

1. Mangal, S. K., & Mangal, Shubhra. Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII-MM). Agra: National Psychological Corporation.

2. Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional Intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books.
3. Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with Emotional Intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books.
4. Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 9(3), 185-211.
5. Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2000). Emotional intelligence as a scientific concept. In *Handbook of Intelligence*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
6. Bar-On, R. (1997). *The Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQ-i)*. Toronto: Multi-Health Systems.
7. Singh, D. (2003). *Emotional Intelligence at Work*. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
8. Aggarwal, J. C. (2008). *Essentials of Educational Psychology*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
9. Best, J. W., & Kahn, J. V. (2011). *Research in Education*. New Delhi: PHI Learning.
10. Garrett, H. E. (2014). *Statistics in Psychology and Education*. New Delhi: Paragon International.
11. Anastasi, A., & Urbina, S. (1997). *Psychological Testing*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India.
12. Thorndike, R. M., & Hagen, E. (1977). *Measurement and Evaluation in Psychology and Education*. New York: Wiley.
13. Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research Methods in Education*. London: Routledge.
14. Koul, L. (2009). *Methodology of Educational Research*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
15. Sharma, R. A. (2006). *Fundamentals of Educational Research*. Meerut: R. Lall Book Depot.

